

Converting Kuwait from Electronic Government to Smart Government

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Abstract— Governments have gone through several different stages, starting from the traditional government or the government of paper, and then the e-government to the smart government, which is an improvement of the e-government. Smart government is characterized by inclusiveness, flexibility and creativity, achieving citizen satisfaction in a modern and advanced Information and communications technology (ICT), as it contributes to be decision-making, participation and infrastructure development, saving time, effort and money. The State of Kuwait has an efficient ICT infrastructure that helps in the transformation process. The research based on the Bayesian belief network (BBN), the model describes the relationships between the variables and to get the most accuracy for the quality services of the e-government portal and evaluate them before converting into smart government. The conversion based on four stages; first plan and policies, second e-government infrastructure evaluation, third e-government service evaluation, fourth implementation and evaluation of smart government. This research also discusses the civil card in its current form and the information it contains and the possibility of developing it by adding a QR code to add information and data to meet the need of the card holder in various regions, and more civil card Smart and effective before.

Keywords-component; Smart government, e-government, Quick Response code(QR)

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is witnessing a rapid development in different areas of life, thanks to that of information and communication technology, and the great change that brought about in different aspects of life, before the emergence of technology, governments were in the traditional stage, which is the stage of papers, handwriting and file storage in the primitive form, and after the development of information technology entered the

term new is the term e-government, which is one of the basics of building advanced governments that keep pace with this tremendous development in information technology. E-government is a set of interactions and relationships that link various components of society with each other.

The main goal of using ICT in e-government is to enhance information and provide services to encourage citizen participation in e-government initiatives (Holmes 2001) [1]

E-government played a prominent and important role in developing governments and reducing the documentary cycle and red tape in governmental and non-governmental transactions.

With the speedy increase in the speedy and massive technological development in the field of communications and information and the entry of smart devices, the concept of smart government was launched, which accompanies this rapid development in the field of technology, because smart government is an extension of electronic government, but it is more effective, comprehensive and flexible that contains many applications and smart services that can be accessed from Any place, any time.

The State of Kuwait has been keen on keep pace with the rapid development in the world of communications and information, and this has contributed to Kuwait's ability to transform into a smart government because of its components and infrastructure.

The contribution of this research is as follows:

- Development of e-government and its infrastructure in Kuwait to transform it into a smart government.
- Developing proposals and solutions to turn Kuwait into a smart government.

This research was organized as follows:

Section 2 presents modern research for smart government, Section 3 provides the ingredients for the State of Kuwait, Section 4 provides methods and solutions for transformation into smart government, Section 5 introduces a civil ID model. In section 6, add the QR code to the civil card, Section 7 presents the results of the experiment on the civil card, and the research were finally concluded in Section 8.

1.1. Overview

The smart government, through smart mobile electronic services aims at improve the relationship between citizens and the government of the State of Kuwait. An effective smart government will help enhance participation in decision-making and make institutions more transparent and accountable. The implementation of smart government in Kuwait will solve many of the problems encountered by citizens and residents. From this standpoint, the research problem arises about the possibility of developing governmental infrastructure towards a smarter government.

Smart government in its limited concept is to convert electronic services into smart mobile devices such as smart phones and tablets, while smart government in its broad concept will touch all aspects of life so that there is an identification activity for every citizen and resident who contains all the information and personal transactions with government agencies.

Converting e-government into smart government in Kuwait faces important challenges and obstacles represented in: financial resources - legislative policies and laws - communication and information technology infrastructure - the amount of open data provided by government institutions that do not conflict with the violation of personal rights - the degree of confidence in the integrity of the data and the mechanism that will be applied to ensure the integrity of the data - The ability of government institutions to deal with the vast amount of data - Governance that can deal with the new concept of smart government - The availability of technical cadres necessary to implement and manage the smart government, and finally the required cooperation between all segments of society (government - citizens - the private sector). All of the above-mentioned challenges, led to a lack of confidence by the service

recipient [2,3,4,5]

Figure 1 Challenges Related to Big Data collection and management [6]

The sheer volume of data (the big data) contains all civil information for citizens and residents, companies, workforce,

electricity and water, traffic, judiciary, education, health, trade, and electronic services, which have been collected over the years.

There are challenges for collecting and preparing large data, one of these challenges is using an efficient platform; including servers, storage, and high-performance. Cloud computing is an essential for large data collection, classification, and distribution. There are also challenges related to the skilled IT technical staff to ensure data collection integrity, and data management in an ideal way so that the government can employ them appropriately. Figure (1) identifies some types of challenges related to collecting and managing big data[2,3,4].

2. RELATED WORK

Several researchers point out that there is no general acceptable definition for the smart government; it is an essential step next to e-government with the extensive use of ICT, with smart government e-services perform better, more interaction and transparency with people. (Anthopoulos&Reddick,2016)[7].

Smart government refers to the use of innovative combination of information and communication technologies and the government services, processes, and policies throughout smart-phone applications, mobile government, and social networking to improve public services and achieve the government transparency in all of its policies and transitions.(A.Guenduez,2018)[8].There are fourteen features of smart government: innovation, integration, evidence-based, citizen first, creativity, efficiency, effectiveness, sustainability, equality, entrepreneurship, openness (transparency), citizen engagement, technology distinctive, and resiliency. (A.Guenduez,2018) [8].Smart government goals can be summarized by four main points that distinguish smart government (Elastic - mobile - social - sensors)[9].

Building smart government depends on the technological infrastructure that consists of the information infrastructure represented in (The Internet of things and open data, cloud technology, bridging the digital divide and cyber security) [2], and human resources that play the main role in the smart government for their presence in the government sector[3].The Finance resource is an important factor in building smart government; the transformation needs to plan and monitor the optimal use of financial resources, providing adequate financing for innovation in the field of information and communication technology[4].Laws and institutional regulations are needed to build smart government [5].Smart government is characterized by a set of benefits that lead to building a smart society with advanced smart technology, more effective-decision makers – participation- infrastructure development-providing time, effort and money for all classes of society. The smart government makes it easier for analysts and citizens to review government decisions and express opinions [2,3,4,5].

This research is characterized by using a success model to measure the performance of the E-Government portal, and the dependent variables associated with the quality of service to improve it. [10]. In addition, to facilitate the process of conversion into the smart government. Previous studies have attempted to identify the quality criteria and variables and determine the factors that affect the performance of E-Government Portals. It was difficult to define these criteria and variables, and this research addressed these limitations.

To link the elements of quality of service and the transition to the smart government, the questionnaire was designed as a measuring tool to assess the quality of e-government services, and test its effectiveness in the expectations of service recipients when implementing the smart government. The research also included smart phone applications and social networks and the establishment of a historical record of the activities of the beneficiaries of the service, to improve performance and achieve government transparency in all its decisions and transformations. The research has taken into consideration highlighting the advantages of the smart government through the points covered in the questionnaire, which included creativity, efficiency and effectiveness, innovation, transparency, distinguished technology, integration of services, and citizen participation in decisions related to E-Government Portal services.

2.1. Methodology

In order to achieve the objectives of the research, the researcher used the descriptive analytical method through which the researcher tries to describe the research phenomenon, and to analyze its data, the relationship between its components and the concepts that are presented around it, and the processes it includes and the effects that it causes.

One of the objectives of this research is to assess the e-government services and their quality, before converting into a smart government, based on the Bayesian belief network (BBN) Figure 2. The model is a network that describes the relationships between the variables and shows the possibilities of the variables to get the most accuracy for the quality services of the e-government portal and evaluate them, thus determining whether they are "effective" or "poor" [10].

The research presents the quality standards and determined the factors that affect the performance of e-government before converting into smart government. The question for the end user is whether the software product supports practical and efficient functions for the task for which it was developed. In addition, the software testability and maintainability, the extent to which bugs can be easily identified and resolved, and a degree that enables users to see if the system is appropriate for their needs. The quality model for evaluating e-government portals based on ISO / IEC 25010[10].

A questionnaire was designed to identify the public opinion of citizens and residents regarding the contents of the civil card; the objective is to determine the efficiency of the civil card in its current state, and to determine the information and data that

the citizen and resident need, and are not present in the current design. The random sample consisted of 238 citizens and residents, randomly selected so that the sample includes: 40% 18-30 years old, 21% 31-40 years old, 24% 41-50 years old, and 15% over 50 years old.

Figure 2 Bayesian belief network(BBN) model
(the red ellipses indicate post implementation quality)

3. THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE STATE OF KUWAIT

The State of Kuwait has kept Public Authority for Civil Information (pace) with the progress in ICT and is modernizing the infrastructure of information systems according to the latest international systems. The Central Agency for Information Technology(CAIT), established Kuwait Information Network (KIN) to link all government agencies. In year 2020, about 85 government agencies able to exchange information between each other, it is characterized by a high information security; all are under the umbrella of Kuwait Online Government (KOG). The number of electronic services provided through the e-government portals reached 320 services [11].

The government of Kuwait uses a set of e-government applications designed by the Central Agency for Information Technology(CAIT)[12]. Human resources in the field of information technology are considered one of the challenges of Kuwait government due to the lack of trained IT personnel, as 60%of the IT workforce are foreigners[13]. Financial resources: We find that The Central Agency for Information Technology (CAIT)budget is largely constrained by the Ministry of finance, and the budget allocation takes a long time to be approved [14]. On the part of communication and information technology in education, about 48% of educational institutions use smart devices for education[13],and in the field of the telecommunications

sector, there are only three telecom companies[15].In year2014,the Telecommunications Regulatory Authority and the Electronic Crime Law issued set of laws and regulations such as electronic transaction rules and constrain[16]. Therefore, when converting to a smart government, consideration must be given to the requirements for transformation: applying government concepts, raising efficiency, training human resources, educating the public, expanding service delivery and increasing infrastructure efficiency and open data [17].

The State of Kuwait has encountered several challenges in implementing the smart government: Financial support to implement the conversion faces a complex cycle in the Ministry of Finance, the process takes long time until the budget is approved. [18].The conversion process requires cooperation between all parts of society (government - citizens - the private sector) [19], governance [17],Open data [19] and the huge government data. As for the human resources, all government agencies suffer from a severe shortage in IT trained and experienced Kuwaiti employees [17]

Figure 3 Transformation strategies

4. CONVERTING E-GOVERNMENT INTO SMART GOVERNMENT IN KUWAIT

The State of Kuwait has telecommunications and information systems infrastructure that enables it to transform into a smart government within a short period of time. This research will present methods that will contribute to transforming Kuwait into a smart government. The road map for transforming Kuwait into a smart government consists of four stages.

4.1. First stage

All Developing the transformation plan and policies, which is the stage of setting rules and starting the transformation, and this is done through: The mandate of the Central Agency for Information Technology (CAIT) to implement the transformation process to smart government. The Process starts with setting plans and policies - defining the time period - linking between government agencies - establishing an information security department - establishing a laboratory to determine the viability of new programs and applications - providing secure communication channels between all government sectors, the private sector and individuals - developing information services, social media, and government response [20] CAIT also follows four main tracks of the transformation process: Analyze the current status of e-government - building an environment in which smart government grows –Setup a flexible and integrated infrastructure - Understand the requirements of service recipients to achieve their satisfaction. [20].

Transformation into a smart government needs a set of strategies necessary to complete the transformation process, and presenting it in an appropriate manner that meets the needs of the government, individuals and the private sector (Figure 3).

4.2. Second stage

Developing and equipping:

1- Governance and policies: Setting policies and goals and ensuring that there are no abuses. Ensure that the governance model controlled by high leadership needed for the road map to an advanced smart government transformation. Governance and policies will lead to efficient governmental decisions, cooperation, structure and design of government agencies, administrative linkage between them and transparency [21]. 2- Information technology infrastructure: One of the most important pillars of smart government, smart government is not just information or data that are provided on smart devices, therefore, the best technologies and applications must be used, such as: the use of hybrid applications, it is considered one of the smart web applications that are characterized through development and use. Application Programming Interfaces (API) is the interface for existing and new applications, as well as the data channel, which is available in various forms of mobile phone messages (SMS) and Unstructured Supplementary Service Data(USSD), it is free of charge and widely available [21]. 3- Human resources: It is the main factor in building smart government, therefore, The Central Agency for Information Technology (CAIT) must train and develop national cadres in the government sector, and joint cooperation with the private sector to exchange experiences and make the necessary technical courses, and allow the

charter and developers with active participation, and support the process of education in smart devices to build a new generation capable of keeping pace with rapid technological development [20]. 4- Finance: Kuwait is a rich country, and the budget allocation is not an issue; however, the country needs to allocate a full budget to CAIT to build smart government according to the highest standards and specifications without restrictions or limitation or long process cycle for approval[20]. 5- Security: CAIT must build a dedicated data center for information and data security; whose function is to monitor all attacks and security breaches, and respond quickly to all cases. There is a need for government agencies to ensure that all smart services that you launch for the public from official government websites, and warn the public about unapproved services to ensure the protection of sensitive information and data. The secured data center also analyzes the source code of applications to identify vulnerabilities, and monitors all installed programs and applications [20].

6- Citizens: The main partner in the process of transforming into smart government; therefore, it is necessary to ensure that services reach all groups of society, and that citizens' satisfaction is achieved. CAIT should also ensure the participation of the public through social networks and social media, give opinions and contributions and participate in decision-making [21].

4.3. Third stage

Transforming services, it is necessary to set priorities, evaluate the service to be converted, determine its components and standards, determine the category used for the service, the volume of transactions and use, and determine the added value of the smart service, and will it contribute to increasing the state's revenues?

CAIT adds continues improvements to implement smart government by changing the structure of electronic services in the government sector, providing the best services to the public in smart ways, and integrating a set of electronic services with a single portal, transparency, flexibility, and easy access to smart services. CAIT must take a set of recommendations that contribute to the rapid transformation of a smart government such as open data, provide the appropriate service structure for government agencies, participate in smart initiatives provided by the business sector. In addition, technical support and training for government sector employees and understand the citizens 'needs for the smart services [20,22].

4.4. Fourth stage

Smart government evaluation, this is the last stage of the smart government; during this stage, all previous stages are evaluated and ensuring that they are structured and tested in the correct way. All applications continually checked, ensuring the integrity of data and information, the absence of any security breaches, and ensuring coordination and

interaction between the various authorities.

4.5. Time period

Kuwait is one of the countries that have turned to Information Communication technology (ICT) since the eighties through the civil card. The State of Kuwait has the ingredients that make it very close to the smart government, as it does not need substantial changes in the IT infrastructure, however, applications and programs must be revised. The time period for the start of the smart government is estimated to be between 18 to 24 months. The four stages are divided as follows: First stage, 6 months for general evaluation drawing the transformation process. Second and Third stage will take 10 to 12 months. Fourth stage, the evaluation and trial phase needs 2 to 3 months. The 18 to 24 months are sufficient to convert the e-government into a smart government in Kuwait.

The time periods were estimated according to Al-Alimi,(2018) study for countries around the world [23].

Figure 4 Stages of Smart service

5. CASE MODEL: CIVIL CARD

In this section, we will explain the civil card, its design, and the visible information. The Public Authority for Civil Information (PACI)[24] has made a civil card for all individuals in Kuwait (citizens and residents), and issuing a unified identity, creating a unique civil number for each individual, and creating a unified database. According to PACI statistics, January 2020, the statistics for individual holders of civil card are (1,416,495) for Kuwaitis and (3,234,514) for residents. This civil card contains a small Integrated Circuit Chip (ICC) in which information is stored by the PACI, and

this card was designed with technologies and algorithms that are difficult to break, and the information is read by a special card reader, when the card is passed through the card reader, the device starts the authentication process and then communicates with the application servers. The card reader can access the information stored on the card and decode it so that it can transfer information by radio frequencies, the storage capacity is limited, and there are several layers of security that are difficult to counterfeit, the civil ID is used to verify identity and conduct transactions in the public and private sectors. In addition, the civil ID can be used to travel to the Arab Gulf countries. The visible information on the card includes: the personal photo - name - gender - nationality - address - blood type - date of birth - (for evaluators also contains the passport number - profession) as shown in Figure 5[25,26].

Figure 5 Civil ID

As it shows the statement of the readable area automatically MRZ on the back of the card according to the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) for use in international and mobility systems. Personal information of the card holder is confidential and protected by encryption, the encryption can only be decrypted by authorized personnel[25,26].

Public keys are one of the best ways to achieve data confidentiality and integrity through a civil card. The public-key Infrastructure (PKI) is a set of coding programs and technologies that enable PACI to protect the Internet and communications security and operations. Public Authority for Civil Information (PACI) issues a set of digital certificates using PKI such as the card ID certificate issued for each card, a certificate of signature and authentication to ensure the card holder and electronic signature, digital certificates for companies, all government and non-governmental agencies are included in the digital certificates as part of the electronic services.

Digital certificates rely on PKI public key encryption that contains one public key stored within the digital certificate and published in the repository, one private key stored in the digital certificate holder [25,26].

Steps to read the card in the reader device: 1- Request for authentication (civil card) 2- Respond to the authentication message (card reader) 3- Obtain the application ID (civil card) 4- Encrypted application, the ID, user ID and MAC message authentication code by (card reader) (5) Entering data into the card (civil card), as shown in Figure 6[27].

Figure 6 Authentication process in smart card

5.1. A questionnaire

A questionnaire was designed to solicit public opinions of citizens and residents; a random sample consisted of 238 citizens and residents. The sample included: 40% from 18-30 years, 21% from 31-40 years, 24% from 41-50 years, 15% more than 50 years old. The researcher described the data analysis of the questionnaire results. Multiple answers also analyzed for choosing more than one answer to the same question. Finally, the researcher studied the type and strength of the link between the studied phenomena. The objective was to identify the efficiency of the civil card in its current state, and to identify the information and data needed by the individuals and not present in the current design. The card holders felt that it needs additional information and data in order to be more comprehensive and effective, and not just an identification card. Un the next section we will redesign the civil ID card by adding the QR code and identify the pros and cons.

Placing the QR response code on the civil card made it smarter and more user-friendly, and the open data is available all the time without any effort or additional transactions.

7. PROS AND CONS OF QR CODE

The current civil card contains data on the back of the card, and this data can only be read by a reader and is not available everywhere. However, adding a QR code will provide additional information that was not available in the current design. Data and information can also be read via the smart phone camera or other similar devices equipped with camera or QR scanner and it is available every time and everywhere.

Pros.: 1-The QR code has become easy to use, the information and data in the civil card can be read through smart devices that use (IOS - Android) or scanner devices, unlike the current card that contains Simcard can only be read through a special device.2- It provides data and information that can be obtained anytime and anywhere without compromising the contents.3- The new card can cover a wide range of information from governmental, non-governmental, commercial, and service departments without the need for additional documents.4- Save time, effort and cost.5- Keeping pace with the rapid changes in the world of technology.6- Ease of use by smart phone camera.7- Providing data and information is also smooth and the ability to summarize a lot of information in a small space.8- Reducing the documentation cycle, and contributing to preserving the environment, as it will reduce printing.9-The symbol can be photographed on a smart phone device and kept without the need to hold a civil card.10- Beneficial for both businesses and customers. 11- Store the information for future needs.12- The mobile camera does not have to be lined-up in order to read the QR.13- The information is available regardless where you are; stores, libraries, business, and healthcare. 14- QR codes can be used on ID cards and used for everything.

Cons.:1- QR information can be printed on paper or stored on smart phones, thus displaying the information without the cardholder's knowledge.2- The codes strongly depend on a mobile device or smart phone. 3- Disabling the link or changing QR code is a very difficult process. 4- Data transmission can lead to a security problem.5- QR code can be distorted or scratched.6- Poor camera quality.7- Smart phone is expensive.

8. CONCLUSION

The smart government is the new approach for all countries looking after the welfare of the citizen, and to provide integrated services with the best means of modern communication and information technology. The State of Kuwait is characterized by its development in the field of communications and information because of its infrastructure that contributes to its transformation into a smart government, so we tried to develop a proposal to transform the e-

government to a smart government in the State of Kuwait. The research presented the civil card design in its current form, and the recognition of lack of information needed by the cardholder to be more effective and comprehensive. The researcher introduced a QR code to the civil ID to be more intelligent and comprehensive. The new information makes it easier for the holder to benefit in various aspects and areas of life. This research presented the pros and cons associated with the QR code.

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